

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN: 2349-7750

INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES

Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

ANALYSIS OF ADVANTAGES OF USING ENDOSCOPIC SEPTOPLASTY WITH SYMPTOMS OF DEFLECTED NASAL

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Article Received: November 2019 Accepted: December 2019 Published: January 2020

Abstract:

Introduction: Septal deviations are the most common cause of nasal obstruction, representing a common compliant in rhinologic practice. **Aims and objectives:** The main objective of the study was to analyse the advantages of using endoscopic septoplasty with symptoms of deflected nasal. **Material and methods:** This descriptive study was conducted in Rawalpindi Medical University, Rawalpindi during January 2019 to October 2019. Patients for the study were selected during routine OPD who were diagnosed with deviated nasal septum according to the mentioned criteria. The patients were counselled and explained the procedure and consent for the procedure was taken in the prescribed format. **Results:** The present study includes 415 patients diagnosed with Deviated Nasal Septum as per the mentioned criteria. Their clinical features, endoscopic and CT scan findings were studied in detail as per the pretested Proforma. Average nasal obstruction score significantly reduced at post-op 1 month and post-op 3–6 months follow-ups compared to the pre-op score ($p < 0.001$ for both the follow-ups). **Conclusion:** It is concluded that endoscopic septoplasty is indicated to correct isolated septal spur deformity, posterior septal deformity, nasal valve obstruction and septal spur leading to contact area, persistent headache and atypical facial pain.

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Please cite this article in press Kulsoom Bibi et al., Analysis Of Advantages Of Using Endoscopic Septoplasty With Symptoms Of Deflected Nasal., Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2020; 07[01].

INTRODUCTION:

Septal deviations are the most common cause of nasal obstruction, representing a common complaint in rhinologic practice. Since its introduction, procedures for correction of nasal septal deformities have undergone several modifications, from radical septal resection, to possible preservation of septal framework and nasal mucosa [1]. Frequently, septal deformities can be associated with lateral wall diseases or may be the cause of them. A significantly deviated nasal septum has been implicated in epistaxis, sinusitis, obstructive sleep apnoea and headaches attributable to contact point with structures of lateral nasal wall [2].

For this reason, correction of septal deformities cannot be separated from treatment of disorders of the lateral wall when present. Thus, endoscopic septoplasty is a useful technique for treating symptomatic deformities, but also for improving intraoperative surgical access to lateral nasal wall surgeries (e.g. dacryocystorhinostomy, functional endoscopic sinus surgery)[3]. Septoplasty is one of the commonly performed operations in otorhinolaryngology practice.

It is the definitive treatment for a deviated nasal septum. When it deviates into one of the cavities, it narrows that cavity and impedes airflow. Often the inferior turbinate on the opposite side enlarges, which is termed compensatory hypertrophy [4]. Deviations of the septum can lead to symptomatic nasal obstruction. The evolution of surgical approaches to the correction of a deviated septum includes classic sub-mucosal resection, traditional septoplasty and extracorporeal techniques. Traditional septoplasty techniques were initially described by Killian and Freer [5]. Septoplasty is classically performed under direct visualization using a headlight and nasal speculum. Complications of traditional septoplasty were reviewed, with an emphasis on prevention and treatment. The recently popularized endoscopic septoplasty is a significant advance in septal surgery. Endoscopic technology greatly enhances

visualization during septoplasty. Discrete septal pathologies such as isolated deflection, spurs, perforations, and contact points can be addressed in a directed fashion. These advantages can be especially important in revision cases. Endoscopic technique in conjunction with video imaging is valuable for the education of residents and staff [6].

Aims and objectives

The main objective of the study was:

- To analyse the advantages of using endoscopic septoplasty with symptoms of deflected nasal.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

This descriptive study was conducted in Rawalpindi Medical University, Rawalpindi during January 2019 to October 2019. Patients for the study were selected during routine OPD who were diagnosed with deviated nasal septum according to the mentioned criteria. The patients were counselled and explained the procedure and consent for the procedure was taken in the prescribed format. The operative procedure was performed with anaesthetic fitness and pre-operative admission 1 day prior to surgery.

Statistical analysis

The data was collected and analysed using excel and all the values were expressed in mean and median.

RESULTS:

The present study includes 415 patients diagnosed with Deviated Nasal Septum as per the mentioned criteria. Their clinical features, endoscopic and CT scan findings were studied in detail as per the pretested Proforma. Average nasal obstruction score significantly reduced at post-op 1 month and post-op 3–6 months follow-ups compared to the pre-op score ($p < 0.001$ for both the follow-ups). Average mouth breathing score significantly reduced at post-op 1 month and post-op 3–6 months follow-ups compared to the pre-op score ($p < 0.001$ for both the follow-ups).

Table 01: The comparison of effect of surgical procedure performed on different symptoms

Parameters (symptoms)	Pre-op	Post-op 1 month	Post-op 3– months	p values	
				Pre-op versus Post-op 1 month	Pre-op versus Post-op 3–6 months
Nasal obstruction	4 (2–4)	2 (0–3)	0 (0–1)	0.001 (Significant)	0.001 (Significant)
Mouth breathing	4 (0–4)	1 (0–3)	0 (0–1)	0.001 (Significant)	0.001 (Significant)
Stuffiness	3 (0–4)	1 (0–3)	1 (0–1)	0.001 (Significant)	0.001 (Significant)
Headache	3 (0–4)	1 (0–2)	0 (0–1)	0.001 (Significant)	0.001 (Significant)
Snoring	3 (0–4)	1 (0–3)	0 (0–1)	0.001 (Significant)	0.001 (Significant)
Concern	4 (1–4)	1 (0–3)	0 (0–1)	0.001 (Significant)	0.001 (Significant)

Septoplasty is a commonly performed surgical procedure aimed at relieving nasal airway obstruction, often in conjunction with other nasal and sinus procedures, such as cosmetic rhinoplasty, Dacryocystorhinostomy and functional endoscopic sinus surgery (FESS). Other indications include rhinologic headache, which is due to irritation caused by the contact of the septum with the lateral nasal wall, and chronic sinusitis secondary to septal deviation [6]. The rationale for developing an endoscopic technique from a traditional “headlight” approach comes from the fact that during common nasal procedures, the surgeon’s view is obstructed due to the narrowing caused by septal spurs or septal deviations [7].

Endoscopy enables the surgeon to localize the spurs and remove them under direct visualization by performing an incision precisely over the spur, thus minimizing surgical trauma. At times if there is any spurter from maxillary crest after spur removal, it can be cauterised under vision immediately and bleeding is controlled [8].

The endoscopic approach to septoplasty provides several advantages over the standard headlight technique [9]. It facilitates accurate identification of the pathology due to better illumination, improved accessibility to remote areas. It allows better understanding of the lateral wall pathology associated with the septal deformity [10].

CONCLUSION:

It is concluded that endoscopic septoplasty is indicated to correct isolated septal spur deformity, posterior septal deformity, nasal valve obstruction and septal spur leading to contact area, persistent headache and atypical facial pain.

REFERENCES:

1. Gupta M, Motwani G. Comparative study of endoscopic aided septoplasty and traditional septoplasty in posterior nasal septal deviations. *Indian J Otolaryngol Head Neck Surg.* 2005;57(4):309–311.
2. Maran AG. Septoplasty. *J Laryngol Otol.* 1974;88:393–402.
3. Siegel N, Glicklich R, Taghizadeh F, Chang Y. Outcomes of septoplasty. *Otolaryngol Head and Neck Surg.* 2000;122:228–232.
4. Gupta N. Endoscopic septoplasty. *Indian J Otolaryngol Head Neck Surg.* 2005;57(3):240–243.
5. Lanza DC, Kennedy DW, Zinreich SJ. Nasal endoscopy and its surgical application. In: Lee KJ, editor. *Essential otolaryngology: head and neck surgery.* 5. New York: Medical examination; 1991. pp. 373–387.
6. Stammberger H (1991) *Functional endoscopic sinus surgery.* B.C. Decker, Philadelphia pp 156–159, 430–434
7. Hwang PH, McLaughlin RB, Lanza DC, Kennedy DW. Endoscopic septoplasty: indications, technique and results. *Otolaryngol Head Neck Surg.* 1999;120:678–682.
8. Chung BJ, Batra PS, Citardi MJ, Lanza DC. Endoscopic septoplasty: revisitation of the technique, indications and outcomes. *Am J Rhinol.* 2007;21:307–311.
9. Gandomi B, Bayat A, Kazemei T. Outcomes of septoplasty in young adults: the nasal obstruction septoplasty effectiveness study. *Am J Otolaryngol Head Neck Med Surg.* 2010;31:59–62.
10. Lanza DC, Kennedy DW, Zinreich SJ. Nasal endoscopic and its surgical applications. Lee KJ, editor. ed. *Essential otolaryngology, head and neck surgery.* New York (NY): Medical Examination Publishing Co.; 1991. p. 373-87.